

EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS BASED ON CAREER DEVELOPMENT: EMPIRICAL STUDY AT THE MARITIME PUBLIC SERVICE AGENCY UNDER THE JAKARTA TRANSPORTATION HUMAN RESOURCES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY

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Abstract

This study is intended to analyze and also to answer the existence of research gaps in various research results, in addition to the occurrence of a phenomenon where Job Satisfaction functions as an inconsistent intervening variable that can explain Employee Performance. Things like that are the considerations for conducting this study. This type of research is quantitative descriptive with the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis method on the LISREL application. The research objects used in this study are Work Unit Employees in 3 Public Service Agencies (BLU) Education and Training (Diklat) under the Human Resources Development Agency (BPSDM) of Sea Transportation in DKI Jakarta and Banten with a population of 344 employees and a research sample of 185 employees. The results of this study can be explained that all exogenous variables in this study can explain their influence significantly and are positively correlated with endogenous variables. These results are expected to help management in organizing and maximizing its human resources.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Support, Servant Leadership, Career Development, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance.

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In order to fulfill reliable and competent human resources in Transportation, concrete efforts are made through the implementation of educational pathways, both formation training, competency improvement training, and other technical training, as regulated by Presidential Regulation Number 51 of 2012 concerning Human Resources in Transportation, namely human resources in the transportation sector who must have competence in the transportation sector in accordance with the types of competences determined for positions through formal and non-formal education pathways.

Human resources in the transportation sector include human resources in the fields of traffic and road transportation, railways, shipping, aviation, multimodal transportation and include human resources who function as regulators, transportation service providers, and workers in the transportation sector (BPSDM, 2020).

BPSDM Transportation in realizing reliable and competent human resources in Transportation is through a series of education and training, research and development, planning, placement, expansion of job opportunities, with long-term targets as directed by the President in implementing the Nawacita mission and achieving the targets of the Vision of Indonesia 2045

to build dynamic, productive, skilled hard-working human resources, mastering science and technology supported by industrial cooperation and global talent through human resource development, which is realized through vocational education and training (BPSDM, 2020).

The Center for Development of Marine Transportation Human Resources is an element that implements the duties and functions of the Transportation Human Resources Development Agency which is under and directly responsible to the Head of the Transportation Human Resources Development Agency. The Center for Development of Marine Transportation Human Resources has the task of implementing human resource development in the field of marine transportation. Meanwhile, the Center for Development of Transportation Apparatus Human Resources is an element that implements the duties and functions of the Transportation Human Resources Development Agency which is under and directly responsible to the Head of the Transportation Human Resources Development Agency.

The Center for Development of Transportation Apparatus Human Resources has the task of implementing management education and training for transportation apparatus human resources. Meanwhile, for the implementation of education and training, the implementation is carried out by the Technical Implementation Unit (UPT) within the Transportation Human Resources Development Agency which is directly responsible to the Head of the Transportation Human Resources Development Agency. As for the guidance, in the technical administrative aspects it is delegated to the Secretary of the Transportation Human Resources Development Agency. Then the guidance and guidance in the technical operational aspects of education and training are delegated to the Head of the respective Transportation Human Resources Development Center. The Technical Implementation Unit (UPT) within the Sea Transportation Human Resources Development Agency based on corporate grade and Business Development has changed to the Public Service Agency (BLU) Work Unit (Satker).

The Public Service Agency (BLU) in its implementation does not only provide services to the core business as a source of income, but has the opportunity to obtain income from other sources. In seeking other sources of income, the ability to explore business opportunities through business development is needed without forgetting the duties and functions of the Transportation BPSDM Work Unit.

The Business Field and Business Development Division at the BLU Work Unit are given autonomy to be able to read business opportunities and establish cooperation with work partners. Even the head of the UPT at the BLU Work Unit fully supports the Business Sector and Business Development Division to increase the income of the BLU Work Unit in accordance with applicable laws and regulations.

Even the Public Service Agency (BLU) is given flexibility in financial management that operates with the principles of efficiency and productivity to support the achievement of people's welfare and improve the nation's life. Professional management of the BLU Work Unit needs to be supported by professional staff who are regulated by a proportional remuneration system.

BLU is like a corporation but is oriented towards public service, with a corporate grade system that is expected to be fair and proportional in appreciating the performance of BLU managers so as to improve the performance of the Public Service Agency. However, in reality, based on the BPSDM Performance Report (BPSDM, 2020), there are several BLU performances that have not yet achieved the targets that have been set, such as the realization of budget absorption which did not reach 100% due to the failure to carry out activities, the realization of the number of training participants below the target such as in Formation Education (90.96%), Inauguration Training (55.95%), Functional Technical Training (98.15%), Cooperation (24.39%). In addition, the absorption rate for graduates of the new transportation training program has only reached 79.82%.

Many factors can cause the target not to be achieved at the Public Service Agency (BLU) Diklat BPSDM Sea Transportation Work Unit. According to (Tarmidi & Arsjah, 2019:30) states that internal employee factors have a positive effect on employee performance directly and indirectly on organizational performance. Employee performance has a positive impact on organizational performance.

Meanwhile (Showkat, Shajan, & Pathak, 2019:75) states that the relationship between Strategic Human Resource Management and organizational performance is positive and significant with the mediating role of employee welfare. The results of other studies state that a significant and positive relationship between training and organizational performance, with the mediating role of employee performance also providing positive results on high organizational performance (Mubasher, Naqvi, & Khan, 2013:490).

In the research results of Egenius et al., (2020), Subekti, (2021), showed that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance. Job satisfaction has a significant effect on loyalty. In addition, loyalty has a significant effect on employee performance. And job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance through loyalty. Loyalty moderates job satisfaction on employee performance. The results of Rodrigo et al.'s study (2022) show that there is a positive influence and correlation between job satisfaction and employee performance.

In Hendri (2019), Osman et al., (2015), Putra (2013), Organizational support, Learning organization have a significant and positive effect on job satisfaction and organizational commitment, but do not have a significant effect on employee performance. Job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant effect on employee performance. In the results of Putra's study (2013), (Ridwan et al., 2020), Lestariningsih (2017), Darma & Supriyanto, 2018), organizational support has no significant effect on employee performance, either directly or mediated by job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Job satisfaction.

In the results of Saman's study (2020), compensation has a significant effect on job satisfaction, besides that compensation also has a significant effect on employee performance. By Jamil & Raja (2011), the results of their research show that compensation and performance evaluation practices significantly correlate positively with employee performance.

Darma & Supriyanto (2018), Tahir Masood Quresh, Ayisha Akbar, Mohammad Aslam Khan & Hijazi (2022), The results of the study show that compensation has a significant effect on employee satisfaction, in addition, employee satisfaction can mediate the effect of compensation on employee performance.

The results of other researchers are Afriana (2021), where the results of her research show that the variables of competence and career development have a positive and significant correlation with employee performance. While the job placement variable does not affect employee performance. This implies that local governments can improve employee performance through training and education and a transparent merit system to ensure fairness in career development.

Other researchers Sudiarditha et al., (2019), the results of their research show that placement and career development have a significant effect with a positive correlation with performance through employee job satisfaction at the Ministry of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. The findings of this study found that the existence of employees is one of the triggers for low performance considering the low effectiveness of employees in carrying out their duties and responsibilities.

Other research results such as those conducted by Ratnasari et al., (2019), are that career development has a direct effect on employee performance, work motivation has a direct effect on employee performance, career development has a direct effect on job satisfaction, work motivation has a direct effect on job satisfaction, job satisfaction has a direct effect on employee performance, career development has an indirect effect on employee performance through job satisfaction, and work motivation has an indirect effect on employee performance through job satisfaction.

In Katharina & Kartika (2020), where the results of the study showed that all hypotheses were accepted. Career development has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, career development has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance and job satisfaction mediates the effect of career development on employee performance.

HYPOTHESIS

- H₁: Perceived Organizational Support has an effect on Job Satisfaction.
- H₂: Servant Leadership has an effect on Job Satisfaction.
- H₃: Career Development has an effect on Job Satisfaction.
- H₄: There is an effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Performance.
- H₅: There is an effect of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance.
- H₆: There is an effect of Career Development on Employee Performance.
- H₇: There is an effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance.

Figure 1: Research Framework Model

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive study using a quantitative approach to hypothesis testing with the object of the study being the Work Unit Employees in 3 Public Service Agencies (BLU) of Education and Training (Diklat) under the Human Resources Development Agency (BPSDM) of Sea Transportation in DKI Jakarta and Banten. The number of Work Unit Employees at the BLU BPSDM Sea Transportation as a population is 344 employees. Furthermore, the researcher used a sampling technique by means of proportional random sampling, the determination of sample members the researcher took representatives from each group in the population whose number was adjusted to the number of subject members in each group, to determine the minimum sample needed if the population is known, then the Slovin formula can be used with the assumption that the level of sampling error tolerated is 5% (Sugiono, 2016):

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size of 1548

e = sampling error rate, which is 5%.

The results of the sample size calculation are as follows:

$$n = \frac{344}{1 + 344 (0,05)^2}$$

$$n = 184,94 \approx 185$$

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Perceived Organizational Support Operational Variables

Variable	Definition Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4	5
Perceived Organizational Support (ξ_1)	is as a perception of support from the organization or the perception of work unit employees about how public service agencies provide support, appreciate employee contributions, and provide assistance when employees need it.	Fairness (X1)	1. Fairness in regulations 2. Fairness in performance achievement awards 3. Fairness in team contribution awards 4. Fairness in awards that bring a good name to the service agency	PO1 PO2 PO3 PO4
		Supervisory Support (X2)	1. Attention to problems faced by employees 2. Providing assistance for problems faced by employees 3. Providing motivation for employee efforts 4. Facilitating employee efforts 5. Supporting new employee ideas.	PO5 PO6 PO7 PO8 PO9
		Organizational rewards and job conditions (X3)	1. Attention to employee welfare 2. pay attention to employee satisfaction 3. provide work facilities according to the employee's job description 4. proud of successful employees.	PO10 PO11 PO12 PO13

Table 2: Servant Leadership Operational Variables

Variable	Definition Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4	5
Servant Leadership (ξ_2)	is the behavior of a leader to provide service using conscience and directing individuals voluntarily in achieving organizational goals.	Empowering (X4)	1. Giving encouragement 2. Giving appreciation 3. Giving direction to be achieved 4. Aligning goals	KM1 KM2 KM3 KM4
		Authenticity (X5)	1. Instilling honesty 2. Giving true statements 3. Consistent in attitude	KM5 KM6 KM7
		Providing direction (X6)	1. Firm and clear in procedures 2. Carrying out procedures 3. Teaching subordinates	KM8 KM9 KM10
		Stewardship (X7)	1. Giving a good example 2. Having traits that are emulated by subordinates 3. Instilling a sense of togetherness	KM11 KM12 KM13

Table 3: Career Development Operational Variables

Variable	Definition Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4	5
Career Development (ξ)	Defined as an activity that prepares employees to develop themselves through a planned career path that contributes to the exploration, formation, success and fulfillment of an employee's career.	Career certainty (X8)	1. Clarity of employee career paths 2. Clarity of employee futures 3. Provision of training for employees	PK1 PK2 PK3
		Career decidedness (X9)	1. Have confidence in your career 2. Career level that matches your competency 3. Career level according to length of service 4. Career level according to education	PK4 PK5 PK6 PK7
		Career decision making self-efficacy (X10)	1. Understand career choice factors 2. Understand career development as a process 3. Increase self-knowledge from interests 4. Increase knowledge from abilities	PK8 PK9 PK10 PK11
		Career exploration (X11)	1. Have awareness and understanding of the career chosen 2. Have the ability in the career chosen 3. Have an interest in continuing the career ladder.	PK12 PK13 PK14
		Career indecision (X12)	1. Unclear career 2. Having anxiety about his career 3. Fear of career commitment 4. Unsure about his career 5. No support for his career	PK15 PK16 PK17 PK18 PK19
		Career planning (X13)	1. Have a mature career plan 2. Understand the existing career levels 3. Have career goals	PK20 PK21 PK22

Table 4: Job Satisfaction Operational Variables

Variable	Definition Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4	5
Job Satisfaction (η)	The emotional attitude of service unit employees towards pleasant or unpleasant experiences in the work that is their duty and responsibility.	Satisfaction with income (Y1)	1. Suitability of salary received 2. Suitability of benefits received 3. Fairness of incentives (services)	KK1 KK2 KK3
		Satisfaction with the work itself (Y2)	1. Nature/type of work 2. Suitability of work with knowledge possessed 3. Suitability of work with skills 4. Suitability with abilities 5. Suitability of work with job responsibilities	KK4 KK5 KK6 KK7 KK8
		Satisfaction with the work environment (Y3)	1. Job security, job comfort 2. Completeness of supporting work facilities 3. Workplace regulations	KK9 KK10 KK11

		Satisfaction with internal working relationships (Y4)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Relationship with fellow employees 2. Relationship with superiors/leaders 3. Cooperation with other functions/sections 4. Relationship with clients 	<p>KK12</p> <p>KK13</p> <p>KK14</p> <p>KK15</p>
		Promotion satisfaction (Y5)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Career clarity 2. Opportunity to receive training 3. Opportunity to continue education 4. Opportunity to get promoted. 	<p>KK16</p> <p>KK17</p> <p>KK18</p> <p>KK19</p>

Table 5: Employee Performance Operational Variables

Variable	Definition Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Code
1	2	3	4	5
Employee Performance (η ₂)	defined as the work results achieved based on the ability of work unit employees to carry out and complete service work in accordance with the responsibilities given to them	Quality of Work (Y6)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Quality of work in carrying out service work 2. Quality of work in completing service work 3. Suitability of service implementation with service standards 4. Suitability of work results with service user expectations 	<p>KP1</p> <p>KP2</p> <p>KP3</p> <p>KP4</p>
		Promptness (Y7)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Punctuality in attendance 2. Punctuality in carrying out work 3. Timeliness in completing work 4. Punctuality in achieving work targets 5. Punctuality according to established time standards 6. Timeliness as promised 7. Timely completion of work exceeds standard time 	<p>KP5</p> <p>KP6</p> <p>KP7</p> <p>KP8</p> <p>KP9</p> <p>KP10</p> <p>KP11</p>
		Initiative (Y8)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Initiative in carrying out work 2. Initiative in completing work 3. Initiative in solving problems 4. Initiative to be careful in carrying out work 5. Initiative in delivering on service promises 	<p>KP12</p> <p>KP13</p> <p>KP14</p> <p>KP15</p> <p>KP16</p>
		Capability (Y9)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ability to carry out services 2. Ability to solve service problems 3. Ability to work in a team 4. Ability to cooperate with leaders 5. Ability to cooperate between functions 6. Ability to cooperate with clients 	<p>KP17</p> <p>KP18</p> <p>KP19</p> <p>KP20</p> <p>KP21</p> <p>KP22</p>
		Communication (Y10)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communicating in carrying out work 2. Communicating in completing work 3. Communicating in a team 4. Communicating with leaders 5. Communicating with other functions 6. Communicating with clients 	<p>KP23</p> <p>KP24</p> <p>KP25</p> <p>KP26</p> <p>KP27</p> <p>KP28</p>

RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Analysis of Research Variable Description

Table 6: Score Range and Categories

Score	Score Interval	Category
1	1,00-1,80	Very Low/ Very Bad
2	1,81-2,60	Low/ Not Good
3	2,61-3,40	High Enough/ Good Enough
4	3,41-4,20	High/ Good

Source: Zikmund, William G., et. al (2010)

Table 7: Suitability of Hybrid Measurement Model – SEM

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Expected Dimensions	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,91	Good Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,067	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Size			
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)</i>	NNFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Normed Fit Index (NFI)</i>	NFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0,88	Marginal Fit
<i>Relative Fit Index (RFI)</i>	RFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Incremental Fit Index (IFI)</i>	IFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Comparative Fit Index (CFI)</i>	CFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 8: Hybrid Model Measurement Analysis (Full Model)

Measurement Model		SLF	STD. Error (SE)	t-Value	Construk Reliability (CR)	Extract Variance (VE)
Latent Variables	Manifest Variables					
Perceived Organizational Support	<i>Fairness (X1)</i>	0.81	0.061	13.29	0,975	0,928
	<i>Supervisory Support (X2)</i>	0.78	0.061	12.72		
	<i>Organizational rewards and job conditions (X3)</i>	0.85	0.058	14.56		
Servant Leadership	<i>Empowering (X4)</i>	0.90	0.056	16.16	0,980	0,925
	<i>Aunthenticity (X5)</i>	0.86	0.057	15.09		
	<i>Providing Direction (X6)</i>	0.89	0.057	15.59		
	<i>Stewardship (X7)</i>	0.80	0.060	13.38		
Career Development	<i>Career certainty (X8)</i>	0.76	0.060	12.67	0,979	0,922
	<i>Career decidedness (X9)</i>	0.84	0.058	14.59		
	<i>Career decision making self-efficacy (X10)</i>	0.86	0.057	15.06		
	<i>Career exploration (X11)</i>	0.86	0.057	15.08		
	<i>Career indecision (X12)</i>	0.84	0.058	14.56		

Measurement Model		SLF	STD. Error (SE)	t-Value	Construk Reliability (CR)	Extract Variance (VE)
Latent Variables	Manifest Variables					
	Career planning (X13)	0.86	0.057	15.16		
Job Satisfaction	Satisfaction with income (Y1)	0.78	0.060	13.04	0,955	0,878
	Satisfaction with the work itself (Y2)	0.86	0.063	13.68		
	Satisfaction with the work environment (Y3)	0.89	0.061	14.50		
	Satisfaction with internal working relationships (Y4)	0.86	0.062	13.82		
	Promotion satisfaction (Y5)	0.89	0.061	14.52		
Employee Performance	Quality of Work (Y6)	0.85	0.058	14.67	0,980	0,942
	Promptness (Y7)	0.94	0.051	18.49		
	Initiative (Y8)	0.90	0.053	17.02		
	Capability (Y9)	0.60	0.065	9.19		
	Communication (Y10)	0,60	0.065	9.20		

Source: Processed data

Table 9: Summary of Latent Variable Inter-Test Results

No	Structural Path	Path Coefficient	t-Value	t-table	Test Results
1	Perceived Organizational Support (PO) → Job Satisfaction (KK)	0.21	2.76	1.96	Significant
2	Servant Leadership (KM) → Job Satisfaction (KK)	0.35	3.92	1.96	Significant
3	Career Development (PK) → Job Satisfaction (KK)	0.40	5.33	1.96	Significant
4	Perceived Organizational Support (PO) → Employee Performance (KP)	0.25	2.75	1.96	Significant
5	Servant Leadership (KM) → Employee Performance (KP)	0.19	2,54	1.96	Significant
6	Career Development (PK) → Employee Performance (KP)	0.28	3.73	1.96	Significant
7	Job Satisfaction (KK) → Employee Performance (KP)	0.39	4,31	1.96	Significant

Source: Processed data

B. Structural Equation

Sub Structural Equation 1

$$KK = 0.21*PO + 0.35*KM + 0.40*PK, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.32, R^2 = 0.68$$

$$\begin{matrix} (0.076) & (0.089) & (0.075) & (0.069) \\ 2.76 & 3.92 & 5.33 & 4.60 \end{matrix}$$

Sub Structural Equation 2

$$KP = 0.39*KK + 0.25*PO + 0.19*KM + 0.28*PK, \text{Errorvar.} = 0.14, R^2 = 0.86$$

(0.090)	(0.091)	(0.0.75)	(0.074)	(0.060)
4.31	2.75	2.54	3.73	3.29

Figure 2: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) Standardized

Figure 3: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) t-Value

Table 10: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis		Hypothesis Description	Path Coef./R2	t _{value} /F _{value}	t _{table} /F _{table}	Test Results
H1	$H_0 : \gamma_{11} = 0$	Perceived Organizational Support has no effect on job satisfaction	0.21	2,76	1,96	H₀ is rejected H_a is accepted. Perceived Organizational Support has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction
	$H_a : \gamma_{11} \neq 0$	Perceived Organizational Support has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction				
H2	$H_0 : \gamma_{12} = 0$	Servant Leadership has no effect on job satisfaction	0.35	3,92	1,96	H₀ is rejected H_a is accepted Servant Leadership has a significant influence and is positively correlated with job satisfaction.
	$H_a : \gamma_{12} \neq 0$	Servant Leadership has a significant influence and is positively correlated with job satisfaction.				
H3	$H_0 : \gamma_{13} = 0$	Career development has no effect on job satisfaction	0.40	5,33	1,96	H₀ is rejected H_a is accepted Career development has a significant influence on job satisfaction and is positively correlated.
	$H_a : \gamma_{13} \neq 0$	Career development has a significant influence on job satisfaction and is positively correlated.				
H4	$H_0 : \gamma_{21} = 0$	Perceived Organizational Support has no effect on Employee Performance	0,25	2,75	1,96	H₀ is rejected H_a is accepted Perceived Organizational Support has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance
	$H_a : \gamma_{21} \neq 0$	Perceived Organizational Support has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance				
H5	$H_0 : \gamma_{22} = 0$	Servant Leadership has no effect on Employee Performance	0,19	2,54	1,96	H₀ is rejected H_a is accepted Gaya kepemimpinan situasional berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap Kinerja pegawai
	$H_a : \gamma_{22} \neq 0$	Servant Leadership has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance				
H6	$H_0 : \gamma_{23} = 0$	Career development has no effect on Employee Performance	0,28	3,73	1,96	H₀ is rejected H_a is accepted Career development has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance
	$H_a : \gamma_{23} \neq 0$	Career development has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance				
H7	$H_0 : \beta_{21} = 0$	Job satisfaction has no effect on Employee Performance	0,39	4,31	1,96	H₀ is rejected H_a is accepted Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance
	$H_a : \beta_{21} \neq 0$	Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance				

Source: Processed data

- H₁: Perceived Organizational Support has a significant effect and is positively correlated with Job Satisfaction.
- H₂: Servant Leadership has a positive correlation and is significantly influential with Job Satisfaction.
- H₃: Career Development has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a positive correlation.
- H₄: Perceived Organizational Support has a significant effect with a positive correlation on Employee Performance.
- H₅: Servant Leadership has a significant effect with a positive correlation on Employee Performance.
- H₆: Career Development has a positive correlation and is significantly influential with Employee Performance.
- H₇: Job Satisfaction has a significant effect with a positive correlation on Employee Performance.

CONCLUSION

Career Development is the dominant variable in the job satisfaction variable for Work Unit Employees in 3 Public Service Agencies (BLU) Education and Training (Diklat) under the Human Resources Development Agency (BPSDM) for Sea Transportation in DKI Jakarta and Banten, where the job satisfaction variable successfully mediates and explains its influence on the research problem, namely Employee Performance.

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